

IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING "PHYSICS" BASED ON THE INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *This given article presents the methodology of teaching and creating universal educational school physics on the basis of electronic information and educational resources on the basis of the open-source platform of the e-learning environment Microsoft Teams. Currently, it is noticeable that the introduction of information and educational resources on the basis of an integrative approach in the e-learning environment is insufficient. Therefore, this article explores the stages of creating electronic information and educational resources on the Open-Source Platform Microsoft Teams and the organization of training on their basis.*

Keywords: *e-learning, Microsoft Team, integrative approach, electronic resource, IT, teaching methodology, multimedia, open-source platform.*

It is important to suggest that creation and implementation of an information environment ensure the quality of education and improve its management in a general education institution in the field of natural sciences, a systemic study of information exchange processes in the higher education system, an integrated system of information. The task of the educational environment is to develop common conceptual and methodological approaches to improving this environment. In order to find a solution to these problems, it is necessary to improve the education system in general education institutions in the field of natural sciences through information and communication technologies and open-source online platforms. Based on this need, multimedia classes are created in each higher education institution, the process of training highly qualified specialists through digitalization in natural science in secondary educational institutions of our country is accelerated, and their work with international partners is intensified. However, as a result of the analysis of the situation on the ground, the study included a laboratory work "Dependence of the resistance of a conductor on its length, cross-sectional surface and material" in general education institutions in the specialty of natural sciences, online platforms with open source are available, activities in the conditions of digitalization and the improvement of teaching based on it require systematization in some places.

Due to the development of information technology in the 21st century, great changes are taking place in human life. At present time the use of various methods and tools for the effective organization of learning is carried out with the help of intensive pictures. In this regard, much has been done in the process of education, but life itself makes it necessary to do much in this area. At present, although the conditions that hinder the organization of modern education are being eliminated, they still have a negative impact on the process of implementing work in the field of general education in the field of natural sciences:

- teachers' little knowledge about modern means of information and communication;
- insufficient provision of educational institutions with modern teaching aids;
- lack of access or low speed of the Internet, which allows organizing modern education;

- students do not have modern means of organizing training, etc.

It is important to note that education today is impossible to imagine without information and communication tools. Currently, most teachers have less knowledge of modern technologies, they do not know how to effectively use information communication tools and video projectors. This can lead to various problems in organizing quality education. Speaking about the integration of digital technologies, we can note the high efficiency of mailing lists, telnet, yuneset, e-minbar, Microsoft Teams, Pickers, etc. It is well known that with the usual traditional teaching method, the teacher becomes an active student and listener. In such cases, training is focused on mechanical memorization.

It is known to everyone that interdisciplinary integration is the fusion of individual parts or elements, turning into a single whole, cohesion. The concept of "integration" was explained by Spencer in the 18th century. We also considered integration as a factor in the development of thinking and tried to interpret it as a synthesis of interdisciplinary communication and forms of training. Integration means "whole", that is, it is the unification of various parts and elements of the process of development of thinking into a single whole. An integrated approach to education in the field of natural sciences serves to further improve its quality. We want to talk about the role of integration and its importance in general secondary education in the conducted scientific research. The analysis of the methodological aspects of this issue and the study of the methodological aspects of the use of integration lessons in the educational process determine the relevance of the topic of our work. In recent years, much attention has been paid to the use of digital technologies in the field of education, where students' motivation for learning increases due to electronic textbooks, interactive information technologies, electronic textbooks that combine text, graphics, sound and video [1, p. 58].

Additionally, Multimedia, slide projector, computer, laptop, TVs connected to the Internet, telephone lines, smart boards, projectors play the role of intermediaries of the educational system in the open platform of Microsoft Teams. Today, equipping the education system with them provides students with high-quality lessons. The pandemic conditions have proven that the use of digital technologies in the education system gives a good effect. We can consider online lessons conducted through television and zoom as a prelude to the transition to digital education. This process has proven to students that it is possible to get an education without leaving home. Regarding the advantages of the transition to digital education, it is appropriate to note the following [2].

- students will have the opportunity to study where and when they want;
- students will be able to choose subjects and study at home even in remote villages where there is a shortage of specialists;
- a culture of receiving and using information from the Internet is formed;
- raises the education system to a new level, dramatically reduces the cost of time and money;
- the user will have the advantage of not getting lost in the "digital world", will find his place and find a good job.
- transfers topics from textbooks, laboratory work and demonstration experiments in electronic form to the monitor.

Definitely, with the help of the online platform of the open-source Microsoft Teams e-learning environment, the student's ability to think creatively increases when conducting lectures, practical, laboratory and demonstration of experiments in a visual and demonstrative form.

Undeniably, information and methodological support of educational processes means the development of knowledge, skills and competencies that must be acquired by students, at the level of competence based on the requirements established by the State Educational Standard and the Scientific Program, based on the integrated design of the educational process. It includes educational and methodological resources, electronic textbooks, didactic tools and materials, assessment criteria that ensure the receipt of guaranteed results, independent learning and training, as well as the implementation of control, aimed at developing the creative abilities of the student [3].

Definitely, the Microsoft Teams online platform has the ability to perform lab work called "Disclaimer, working with languages and materials of a large number of things" simultaneously in the form of animation, modeling, multimedia and other forms, all data is located in blue and stored in memory based on technology. The advantages of the Microsoft Teams Open Source are that it allows students to control their knowledge in the system, and at the same time, students can easily relearn course topics whenever they want and there are opportunities for quick assessment of students' knowledge during the lesson through the Pickers system [4].

An experimental device for determining the resistance of a conductor as a function of its length, cross-sectional area and material.

By summarizing it can be suggested that it should be said that the use of modern technologies in education, on the one hand, causes certain difficulties and problems, on the other hand, it leads to various achievements. This process is clearly manifested in the further development of students with individual potential.

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